

PROMOTING STUDENT-TEACHER COLLABORATION IN PERSONALIZED LEARNING

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Abstract. *In this article, the scientific views on the issue of improving the technology for the development of teacher-student cooperation in the process of improving the qualifications of future teachers have been considered. At the same time, the concept of person-oriented education, the scientific views of scientists about it, the experience and research work of pedagogues are shown. Necessary factors and bases of development of professional competencies of future pedagogues in cooperation with students were explained.*

Keywords: *person, the concept of person-oriented education, competence, cooperative education, professional competence.*

Introduction

Human capital and economic achievements of the state and society are closely related to each other. Philosopher, sociologist and anthropologist Valery Khan thinks that the quality of pedagogical education is of decisive importance in the innovative development of Uzbekistan. According to him, "New Uzbekistan has started to take steps in this field. In particular, in 2018, the President's decree "On approval of the innovative development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2021" was adopted. It has a complex and far-sighted goal: by 2030, it is planned to include Uzbekistan in the ranks of the 50 most advanced countries in the world in the Global Innovation Index rating. The main goal of the strategy is "the development of human capital as the main factor determining the level of the country's competitiveness in the international arena and its innovative development."

Science and education - these are the things that should create the human capital that ensures the country's competitiveness and its innovative development. Our future depends on it.

One of the important tasks of the Ministry of Pre-School Education is to prepare children for analytical thinking while teaching them modern knowledge in the process of preparing them for school. As the President said, "if we work for 10 years in the system of pre-school education-school-higher education institution, people will appear in our society who will look forward to the future with confidence and who are not afraid of anyone".

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS.

"Individual-oriented teaching technologies or technological approach - an educational activity in which the student's personality is placed in the center of education, and it is envisaged to create conditions for the development of his mental abilities and the realization of his natural abilities (G.K.Selevko) on lessons. In such educational activities, student activity takes a leading place in the educational process.

Their activity, independence, free thinking, initiatives are supported. The teacher's activity consists of guiding, giving advice when necessary, monitoring and evaluating students' behavior. Such activities include problem-based learning, modular learning, working in small groups, differentiated, embodied, individualized learning technologies, developmental, active, brainstorming, blitz games and other learning technologies.

By personalized learning, we mean more interests and needs of students. In this case, the content of education is the student, the main goal is to direct it according to the interests of the person, to support his interests and abilities. A student's self-awareness, personality uniqueness, level of development, actions to achieve future dreams and goals are based on thorough learning and preparation for the next stage of education. His interests and imagination are directed towards a specific goal, and he can be able to protect his interests by acquiring not only the minimum level, but also the maximum level of knowledge in subjects based on the requirements of the State Education Standards. For this, it is very important for teachers to stimulate their aspirations and interests. This approach involves the teacher-student-teacher relationship, which includes the student's learning process in the implementation of education. Cooperation and the principle of free choice does not make him bored in his chosen field, encourages him to improve his knowledge.

The national model of education consists of 5 components: individual, state and society, continuous education, science, production, actually, "person" is in the first place. It is clear from this that the whole educational system is directed to the student's personality, and the person should be at the center of it. Therefore, the teacher should create an educational environment that ensures the personal development of the learner. To date, comprehensive definition of the so-called "person" has not been created. There are different opinions about him. For example, A. V. Petrovsky interprets a person as a unique individual united in the world of other people. In such cases, a system of interpersonal relations is created. The individuality of a person is related to his inner world.

That is why we can say that individual-oriented education is one of the most important types of pedagogical activity. This activity has its specific purpose, tasks, content and many unique pedagogical technologies.

During the lesson the most important task of the teacher is to turn a passive listener into an active creator. The most important factor for this is to increase the student's confidence in his knowledge and abilities. During the implementation of this task, the level of physical, mental and spiritual development of the student is studied, giving them the necessary recommendations, pedagogical support, making corrections and additions to their activities in the necessary places is considered an important stage. When the internal motivation of students is at a high level, their personal independent learning abilities can be active. One of the most effective means of increasing the level of interest in learning and creative activity is the problem-based teaching method.

The emergence of a new paradigm of education is not only related to socio-economic changes, but it occurred in the entire process of cultural development. Humanitarian philosophy and psychology (E. Fromm, J.P. Sartre, V. Frankl, N. Berdyayev, A. Maslow, K. Rogers, etc.) play a key role in its formation. The main goal of this concept is to recognize the uniqueness of each person's life, the fact that each person is unique and individual. Humanistic philosophy recognizes the need for self-realization and self-development as the greatest need of an individual and manifests the ability to accept individual personal choice as a mechanism for self-development and freedom that through taking responsibility for the choices made as an essential condition for their implementation.

Conclusion

In traditional classrooms, the task given by the teacher is often ineffective and boring for the students, it may not be the cause of the learner's laziness or indifference, however, it can be

cause of the inability of the teacher to interest them in the subject being taught. Most lessons are usually organized on the basis of the scheme "explanation - reinforcement of acquired knowledge - homework". As a result, some students' minds and hands will be left empty.

In conclusion, looking through above information, we can say that person-oriented education, by its essence, implies the full development of all participants of the educational process. This suggests that when organizing the educational process, one should not take into account only the personality of the learner, but first of all, it should be approached based on the goals related to the professional activity in the future.

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